

Prospective Comparative Evaluation of STONE Score and GUY'S Score as A Pre-Operative Predictor of Stone Free Rate and Complication in PCNL Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: PCNL remains the gold standard treatment modality for large and/or complex renal stones, because the percutaneous approach to renal stone removal is better than the open approach. Recently few scoring system is introduced aiming to predict pre-operatively the SFR and complication for better patient counselling and surgical planning, The GUY score and STONE Nephrolithometry score are most commonly used scoring system. Here we are comparing GUYS scoring system and STONE Nephrolithometry score for pre op prediction of Stone free rate and post op complication within 30 Days Using Modified Clavien Dindo System.

Methodology: This study was done as a prospective observational clinical study done on 100 patients admitted in Department of Urology, Tirunelveli medical college from February 2023 to June 2024 with urolithiasis, different scores will be given to each patient as per scoring criteria on NCCT and outcome will be measured. Patients undergoing PCNL >12 years were included. Patients who are unfit for GA, having bleeding diathesis, uncorrected coagulopathy, and pregnancy were excluded. All patients underwent routine serum, urine examinations and a NCCT scan preoperatively and Guy's and S.T.O.N.E. score was calculated in all.

Results: In our study population, at the end of 3 months, the treatment was success with absence of stones in 62 patients and in rest of patients; it was failure in 38 patients. We analysed certain parameters related to the outcome. In our study, there was no significant difference in mean age and its relation to treatment outcome. Gender of the patient also had no significant impact on outcome. Coming to stone characteristics, Failure cases had more number of stones with a mean stone number of 1.89. Mean Guys score was 2.57 in failure cases and 1.41 in treatment success cases. Similarly, when we calculated Stones score the mean score was 8.36 in failure cases and 6.93 in success cases. Similarly, complication was more in failure cases.

Conclusion: Our study found that both scoring methods predicted the SFR with similar accuracy, and endourologists can utilize either score in their day-to-day work. In the outpatient department, both score systems can be quickly assigned and used to help with patient counseling. Our study's prospective design, sufficient sample size, and rigorous application of NCCT scan to ascertain stone-free status in the post-operative phase were its strongest points.

Keywords: S.T.O.N.E score, Guy's score, PCNL, Renal stone, Scoring system.

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Introduction

Incidence of urolithiasis is approximately 5-10% population [1]. PCNL (percutaneous nephrolithotomy) remains the gold standard treatment modality for large and/or complex renal stones [2,3], because the percutaneous approach to renal stone removal is better than the open approach in terms of morbidity, convalescence and cost.

PCNL has replaced the open surgical removal of large or complex stone at most institutions [4,5]. Despite highly frequent done surgery in urology it

is frequently associated with post op complication as well as requirement of another surgery due to residual stone. The recommended treatment option for renal calculi and staghorn calculi is percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) according to the guidelines of the European Association of Urology (EAU) [1]. PCNL has increasingly been used over the past few decades and may continue in the future [2,3].

However, PCNL outcomes among the authors are different, because of the vast heterogeneity in the

methods for clinical and academic characterization of nephrolithiasis besides the evaluation of surgical outcomes. So assessing the preoperative factors that affect SFR and complications is critical.

Despite the technique having been introduced for more than 30 years, a standardised method of pre operatively classifying stone disease to accurately predict the SFR and complication is still lacking.

Recently few scoring system is introduced aiming to predict pre-operatively the SFR and complication for better patient counselling and surgical planning ,The GUY,S score and STONE Nephrolithometry score are most commonly used scoring system others are CROES nomogram, the seol national university and renal complexity score are other scoring system used today. The widespread use of a standardized stone scoring system is very precious for counselling patient, clinical decision, and assessment of outcomes, in addition to improving academic reporting [7]. However, no universally accepted stone scoring system for predicting SFR and complications after PCNL exists. Comparison of the stone free status in different clinical studies indicated some advantages as well as disadvantages of one nomogram to another for different variables. Computed tomography (CT) scan has now emerged as a major imaging tool for evaluation of stone disease. Guy's score and STONE score based on CT scan have been externally validated, but the superiority of one over the other has not been ascertained yet.

Here we are comparing GUY, s scoring system and STONE Nephrolithometry score for pre op prediction of Stone free rate and post op complication within 30 Days Using Modified Clavien Dindo System

Material and Methods

This study was done as a prospective observational clinical study done on 100 patients admitted in Department of Urology, Tirunelveli medical college from February 2023 to June 2024 with urolithiasis, different scores will be given to each patient as per scoring criteria on NCCT and outcome will be measured. Patients undergoing PCNL >12 years were included. Patients who are unfit for GA, having bleeding diathesis, uncorrected coagulopathy, and pregnancy were excluded.

All patients underwent routine serum, urine examinations and a NCCT scan preoperatively and

Guy's and S.T.O.N.E. score was calculated in all. Preoperatively, all patients received prophylactic antibiotics during the induction of anaesthesia or therapeutic antibiotics, according to the urine culture obtained before surgery. All PCNL procedures were done by standard technique. Tract dilation was performed with dilators, and an Amplatz sheath was placed.

Nephroscopy was performed with a rigid Storz nephroscope and stone fragmentation was performed with lithoclast. The intraoperative stone-free status was verified with combined fluoroscopy and nephroscopy. A nephrostomy tube was placed at the end of the procedure. Antegrade double-J stent was placed in all patients. Operative time was considered from the beginning of the cystoscopy for ureteral catheter insertion to the end of the nephrostomy placement.

Complete blood counts, blood urea, serum creatinine and serum electrolytes were performed postoperatively in all cases. Surgical complications were graded according to the Clavien system. Blood transfusion was considered for patients with significant blood loss or patients with signs of hypovolemia, refractory to fluid replacement. The S.T.O.N.E. and Guy's scores were calculated for each patient and their correlation with stone-free status, operation time and blood loss were evaluated.

All patients underwent NCCT scan at 3 months postoperatively to calculate the SFR. Success rate was defined as the absence of residual stones or the presence of asymptomatic clinically insignificant residual fragments 4 mm on NCCT scan at 3 months post operatively. All analyses were conducted using SPSS. A P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Categorical variables were compared with the Chi-square test.

Results

In our study of 100 patients, the most common age diagnosed with renal stones were 51-60 years followed by 41-50 and 31-40 years. In our study population, 64 were male and 36 were female in a ratio of 1.77: 1.

Comorbidity was present in 32 patients in our study Stone was on right side in 42 patients, on left side in 58 patients. Single stone was seen in 66 cases; more than one stone was seen in rest of 34 patients.

Table 1: Demographic feature

Demographic Features		
Age In Years	No Of Patients	Percentage
< 20	4	4%
21-30	6	4%
31-40	24	4%
41-50	24	4%
51-60	32	4%
> 60	10	4%
Sex	No Of Patients	Percentage
Male	64	64%
Female	36	36%
Laterality	No Of Patients	Percentage
Left	42	42%
Right	58	58%
Stone Number	No Of Patients	Percentage
Single	66	66%
Multiple	34	34%
Comorbidity	No Of Patients	Percentage
Present	32	32%
Absent	68	68%

In our study population, at the end of 3 months, the treatment was success with absence of stones in 62 patients and in rest of patients; it was failure in 62 patients. We analysed certain parameters related to the outcome.

In our study, there was no significant difference in mean age and its relation to treatment outcome. Gender of the patient also had no significant impact on outcome. Coming to stone characteristics,

Failure cases had more number of stones with a mean stone number of 1.89. Mean Guys score was 2.57 in failure cases and 1.41 in treatment success cases.

Similarly, when we calculated Stones score the mean score was 8.36 in failure cases and 6.93 in success cases. Similarly, complication was more in failure cases.

Table 2: Treatment Outcome

Factors	Treatment Outcome		P Value
	Success(62)	Failure(34)	
Mean Age	44.55±12.31	45.42 ±11.51	0.815
Sex (Male/Female)	36\10	28\10	0.623
Stone Number	1.22±0.12	1.89±0.35	0.015*
Guys Score	1.41±0.23	2.57±0.89	0.006*
Stone Score	6.93±1.89	8.36±2.56	0.005*
Calyx Puncture	1.12±0.52	1.15±0.45	0.246
Complications	10\52	24\7	0.015*

Discussion

This study was done as a prospective observational clinical study done on 100 patients admitted in Department of Urology, Tirunelveli medical college from February 2023 to June 2024 with urolithiasis.

For patients with renal stones, preoperative imaging techniques are essential to obtaining a precise diagnosis and the best possible surgical care. [7]. the optimal Nephrolithometry score should be simple to use, reproducible, and capable of precisely predicting complications and stone-free status. There is currently no widely recognized perfect scoring system, hence it is crucial to

compare the most recent scoring systems in order to promote future research aimed at creating the ideal scoring system. Our study's objective was to assess the Guy's and S.T.O.N.E. grading systems for predicting PCNL problems and stone-free status.

In our study of 100 patients, the most common age diagnosed with renal stones were 51-60 years followed by 41-50 and 31-40 years. In our study population, 64 were male and 36 were female in a ratio of 1.77: 1. Kumar et al and Bozkurt et al in their study had similar age distribution with 67% males and 33% females. [8,9] Comorbidity was present in 32 patients in our study Stone was on right side in 42 patients, on left side in 58 patients.

Single stone was seen in 66 cases; more than one stone was seen in rest of 34 patients.

In our study population, at the end of 3 months, the treatment was success with absence of stones in 62 patients and in rest of patients; it was failure in 62 patients. A few researchers including Bozkurt et al. (75.1%), Kumar et al. (86%), Nourledin et al. (72%), and Okhunov et al. (80%), reported slightly higher success rates. [8-11] while some studies employed conventional X-rays or ultrasonography to determine SFR, our study's slightly lower SFR may have been caused by our stringent criteria for employing NCCT scans to establish stone-free status and the varying experience of operating surgeons. We analysed certain parameters related to the outcome. In our study, there was no significant difference in mean age and its relation to treatment outcome. Gender of the patient also had no significant impact on outcome. Coming to stone characteristics, Failure cases had more number of stones with a mean stone number of 1.89. Mean Guys score was 2.57 in failure cases and 1.41 in treatment success cases.

These findings were consistent with the original study by Thomas et al. [12] Similarly, when we calculated Stones score the mean score was 8.36 in failure cases and 6.93 in success cases. Multiple studies found the reproducibility of S.T.O.N.E. score in detecting SFR status.13. Pre-operative scores was which was consistent with majority of the authors. [10,11] Noureldin et al reported the mean Guy's score and S.T.O.N.E. score as 2.3+0.7 and 7.6+ 0.1 respectively. [10]

Similarly, complication was more in success cases, The results of our complications were similar to those of Mandal et al. (41.7%) and Smith et al. (52%). [14,15] But compared to many other research, our complication rates were higher. [16-18] relatively greater incidence of complications could have been caused by a variety of factors, including a substantial stone burden, a resident training program, and varying surgical expertise.

Conclusion

Our study found that both scoring methods predicted the SFR with similar accuracy, and endourologists can utilize either score in their day-to-day work. In the outpatient department, both score systems can be quickly assigned and used to help with patient counseling.

Our study's prospective design, sufficient sample size, and rigorous application of NCCT scan to ascertain stone-free status in the post-operative phase were its strongest points.

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